

The SM3D framework delivered at ATU-Net Student Leader Forum 2024

Portal Admin

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[SCIENCE NEWS]

From September 11 to 13, 2024, Phenikaa University hosted the ATU-Net Student Leader Forum 2024 (SeLF), an annual event organized by the Asia Technological University Network (ATU-Net), a strategic international alliance of 34 universities from 15 countries. This event brings together exceptional students and young leaders from ATU-Net member institutions and partners, providing a platform for knowledge exchange, and mutual learning, and fostering both regional connections and a global identity.

Photo: ATU-Net Student Leader Forum 2024. Source: Photo courtesy ©2024 Phenikaa University

This year's forum, held at Phenikaa University, centered around the theme "Fostering Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion through Student Leaders." The forum welcomed 45 student leaders from eight countries, including Bangladesh, Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam, as well as representatives from Pangasinan State University (Prof. Marienuelle T. Aquino) and Mindanao State University - Iligan Institute of Technology (Prof. Phyllis Marie Teanco and Dr. Jeric Anthony Arnado).

Dr. Minh-Hoang Nguyen delivered the keynote address, where he presented the SM3D knowledge management framework, emphasizing how Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (D.E.I.) can serve as a long-term driver of innovative capacity [1-4]. Following his speech, an engaging discussion took place between the speaker and student leaders, focusing on the role of cultural values in embracing D.E.I., along with its practical applications and challenges.

Photo: SM3D Framework delivered at the event. Source: Photo courtesy ©2024 Phenikaa University

The details of Dr. Nguyen's presentation are available on PhilPapers at the following URL [5]: <https://philpapers.org/rec/NGUDAA>.

References

- [1] Vuong QH. (Ed.) (2022). *A New Theory of Serendipity: Nature, Emergence and Mechanism*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/8366675858>
- [2] Vuong QH. (2023). *Mindsponge Theory*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.de/dp/8367405145>
- [3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better economics for the Earth: A lesson from quantum and information theories*. AISDL. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>
- [4] Nguyen MH, Vuong QH. (2024). Diversity, equity, and inclusion in the organization: A fresh view through the lens of granular interactions thinking theory. <https://philarchive.org/rec/NGUDEA>
- [5] Nguyen MH. (2024). D.E.I. as a long-term driver of innovative capacity. *ATU-Net Student Leader Forum 2024*. <https://philpapers.org/rec/NGUDAA>

